

BIOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF SOYBEAN GRAIN AND THE INFLUENCE OF CHITOSAN NANO-PREPARATIONS ON GRAIN QUALITY INDICATORS

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Abstract. *The given article presents information on the chemical composition of the nano preparation "Glycine contains", as well as the effect of chitosan nano preparations on tomatoes oil and the indicators of the positive effect obtained from it.*

Keywords: *soybean, protein, oil, grain, chitosan, nano chitosan, nano preparation, encapsulation.*

It is important to suggest that at present time an important task of the food industry is to ensure food security of the population and meet the budget's need for high-quality food products. Besides that, one of the main goals is to stabilize the production of local food products and raw materials, supply the market with safe, environmentally friendly and high-quality food products.

It is known to everyone that soil and climatic conditions of our country are very favorable for growing soybeans. It can be grown as a main and secondary crop in all regions and Karakalpakstan. As it was mentioned above, shelob caused erosion, due to such actions, organic fashionable way for combatting secondary salinity was reduced. When it is necessary to sow a wheat crop, the microclimate of the field and the phytosanitary condition of the soil and microbiological processes in the soil can be improved.

Moreover, soybeans are used to produce butter, margarine, cheese, milk, flour, and confectionery. Soy flour is added to bread and sausage products and increases the nutritional value, taste, and strength of these products. Soy products are recommended for diabetes. Soybean oil makes up 40% of the vegetable oil produced on earth. Soybeans contain minerals such as potassium, calcium, and phosphorus (Ataboyeva, 2004).

The main objective of scientific work is the correct use of nano preparations in order to obtain a safe, environmentally friendly, and high yield of promising soybean varieties and provide the population with high-quality food products.

Leading research centers and universities around the world are conducting many scientific studies on the use of encapsulation and seed treatment with nano preparations before planting agricultural crops.

However, the study of the effect of nano preparations on increasing labor productivity in many countries today is an urgent task and meets the requirements of the future.

The main advantage of soy is the presence of a large amount of protein and oil in its grain.

Soybeans contain a rare complete protein, which is not inferior to animal protein in nutritional value. It contains unique biologically active substances, lecithin, choline, vitamins A, B and E, macro- and microelements and other valuable substances. Soybeans do not contain lactose and cholesterol. It is worth noting that this product is alternatively balanced in terms of caloric value and content of essential nutrients and biologically active substances. [1; 3rd row]

Depending on the soybean variety and growing conditions, the protein content in seeds is usually 37-44%, oil - 17-23%, which in total is 53-67% of these essential substances.

Certainly, the high-quality protein contained in soybeans contains all the amino acids necessary for the life of humans and animals. In its composition, soy protein is very quickly absorbed, very nutritious and close in composition to animal protein.

It is known to everyone that soybeans are used in different industries. Its proteins and oils are used in plastics, glue, plywood, various coatings (for impregnating paper, woolen fabrics), rubber substitutes, explosives, linoleum, paints, varnishes, waterproofing products, printing materials, synthetic gasoline, soap, glycerin, insecticides. Soy protein is used in the production of sausages, cheeses, cottage cheese, canned goods, various sauces, coffee, desserts, cakes, pasta. [2; Pp. 3-4]

According to G. Tangirova [3; P.9], it was shown that while growing soybeans using the Nitragin-137 strain, the amount of protein in the grain increased, and the amount of oil decreased. In order to increase the protein content, high temperature and a sowing rate of 90 kg / ha in the Nitragin-137 Uzbek variant per hectare were used. Variety -2 yielded 1000 kg of protein and 570 kg of oil.

The purpose of the study is to determine the importance of biologically active nano polymers based on chitosan and its derivatives in increasing the morpho-economic characteristics of plant grain, quality indicators and yields based on physiological and biochemical indicators of the soybean plant *Glycine hispida* variety. Based on observations, it consists in issuing scientific opinions and recommendations on the areas of the industry.

Research object and methods. The object of the study was the medium-sized model variety "Nafis" and the hot variety "Sevinch" and the foreign variety "Selekta-302", created in local conditions, as well as nano preparations (chitosan) prepared on the basis of *Bombyx mori* chitosan obtained from the cocoon of the local silkworm at the Institute of Polymer Chemistry and Physics of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan (initial 0.5%, Nano XZ 0.5%, Nano AXZ used 0.5% (4:1)). Before planting, soybean seeds were treated by encapsulation in a 0.5% solution of chitosan preparations.

However, observational, measuring and comparative analyses, phenological, biometric, morphological, physiological, biochemical and statistical methods were used in laboratory and field experiments during scientific research.

Research results and their discussion. The chemical composition of plant grain is one of the important technological indicators of its quality. In order to determine the amount of protein and oil in soybean grain, the following quality indicators were determined in laboratory conditions when analyzing grain samples obtained from experimental varieties. (Table 1)

According to the results of the obtained biochemical analysis, it was established that the amount of protein and oil in the grain changes significantly depending on the genetic characteristics of the variety under the influence of chitosan preparations.

While analyzing the amount of protein in the grain, it was 38.5% in the control variant of Nafis variety, 38.6% in the variant treated with chitosan, 41.2% in the variant treated with nanochitosan, and 41.6% in the variant treated with nanoascorbate chitosan. The amount of oil is 22.7% in the control variant according to the corresponding law, in the variant with the addition of the chitosan preparation. 22.7%, 22.3% in the variant treated with nanochitosan, and 22.6% in the variant treated with nanoascorbate chitosan.

Table 1

Changes in the biochemical composition of soybeans under the influence of chitosan nano preparations. (relative to dry matter, in %, 2023, on average)

№	Experimental variants	Protein content %	Thickness %
Elegant variety			
1	Control	38,5	22,7
2	Chitosan	38,6	22,7
3	Nanochitosan	41,2	22,3
4	Nanoascorbate chitosan	41,6	22,6
Selekta-302 variety			
1	Control	37,7	24,3
2	Chitosan	38,2	23,9
3	Nanochitosan	39,8	23,4
4	Nanoascorbate chitosan	39,9	22,9

Moreover, biochemical analysis revealed a significant difference between the varieties, the protein content of the foreign variety Selecta-302 in the experiment was 37.7% by dry weight in the control variant, 38.2% in the variant treated with chitosan, 39.8% in the variant exposed to the drug nanochitosan, the effect of the drug nanoascorbate chitosan and in the treated variant was 39.9%, while the amount of oil in the control variant was found to be 24.3%, under the influence of chitosan - 23.9%, under the influence of the drug nanochitosan - 23.4%, under the influence of the drug nanoascorbate chitosan - 22.9%.

By summarizing it should be suggested that by treating seeds with chitosan nanopreparations, it is possible to increase the protein content in the grain and achieve high yields. In the local variety Nafis, in our study, higher results were obtained in the variants treated with nanochitosan and nanoascorbate chitosan preparations. Compared with the control, the amount of protein increased by 7.01% in the variant treated with nanochitosan, by 7.05% in the variant treated with nanoascorbate chitosan, and in the foreign variety Selektta-302, the amount of protein in dry weight compared with the control variant increased by 5.6% in the variant treated with nanochitosan, and it was found that it increased by 5.8% in the variant treated with nanoascorbate chitosan.

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